

THE EMERGENCE OF THE LITERARY LANGUAGE AMONG THE SLAVS (PREREQUISITES FOR THE EMERGENCE OF THE RUSSIAN LITERARY LANGUAGE)

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The Russian literary language, as the highest form of the national language, serves the realms of science, education, culture, government, and media, playing a crucial role in conveying information and knowledge. The development of the Russian literary language, which began in the Old Russian and Church Slavonic periods, has undergone a long path of evolution. Over the centuries, it has reflected significant historical events and transformations in the lives of the Russian people [1].

Peter the Great's reforms were a turning point in the history of the Russian literary language. Influenced by Western European culture and the drive towards modernization, Peter I implemented a series of changes that also affected the Russian language. The Church Slavonic language, which had dominated official documents and literature, gradually gave way to a new literary language. During this time, foreign words were actively borrowed to reflect new concepts and realities.

Peter's reforms facilitated the development of secular literature and science, necessitating a language that was comprehensible and accessible to a broad segment of the population [2].

Mikhail Vasilyevich Lomonosov made a significant contribution to the development of the Russian literary language. He set himself the goal of creating a nationwide literary language that is understandable and accessible to all segments of society. To achieve this goal, Mikhail Vasilyevich Lomonosov developed the

theory of the "three calms," according to which there should be three styles in the Russian language:

- High style: for use in scientific, philosophical, and poetic works.
- Medium style: for use in business correspondence, journalism, and fiction.
- Low style: for use in colloquial speech, folklore, and satirical literature.

[3].

Mikhail Vasilyevich Lomonosov also created the first scientific grammar of the Russian language, which consolidated the existing norms and contributed to their unification. Russian spelling rules were also developed by him, and many new words and expressions were introduced into the Russian language.

M. V. Lomonosov's main achievement was the creation of the "Russian Grammar" (1755), in which he laid the foundations of the grammatical system of the modern Russian language. He also developed the theory of the "three calms," distinguishing the use of words and expressions in different styles of speech: high, medium, and low.

Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin played a key role in the development of the modern Russian literary language. He laid the foundations for functional and stylistic differentiation of the language, creating works of different genres and styles. In his historical and journalistic works, Pushkin clearly distinguished the speech of the characters from the speech of the author, using different linguistic means and techniques. His work became a model for subsequent generations of writers and had a huge impact on the formation of the modern Russian literary language [4].

The emergence of the literary language among the Slavs

Classical Old Slavonic, or, as it is more preferable to call it, the Old Church Slavonic language, originated on the South Slavic ethnic soil as a book-written cult language of the Bulgarian and Macedonian Slavs. Church Slavonic languages of various varieties appeared—Serbian, "Russian" (East Slavic), and Middle Bulgarian—which absorbed to a greater or lesser extent elements of the languages of the corresponding Slavic nationalities.

In the X-XI centuries, which include the oldest surviving Slavic monuments of writing, undoubtedly existed as special languages, both the Old Russian (Old Eastern Slavic) and the Old Bulgarian languages. Therefore, F.P. Filin's reproach is that some linguists "believe that the Old Slavic and Old Russian languages were in fact not languages, but dialects of the same common Slavic language."

Historical data indicate that the historical and ethnic identities of the Eastern Slavs were complex. The Eastern Slavs were aware of tribal division and its differences in customs and language. At the same time, they united only a part of the Eastern Slavs with the concept of "Rus," contrasting it with the rest of the Eastern Slavs. Later, the concept of "Rus" was extended to all Eastern Slavs. There was opposition from Russia to the Lyakhs, Czechs, Bulgarians (Danubian), etc. However, at the same time, there was—and this must be emphasised—a consciousness of Slavic unity, unlike foreign-speaking tribes and nationalities—the Ugrians, Volokhs, Chudis, Vesi, Meri, Karelians, etc [5].

So, in the X-XI centuries, there were undoubtedly Old Russian (Old East Slavic) and Old Bulgarian languages serving the respective nationalities. 6

The language of any text (recorded on a tape recorder or a written monument) is directly studied as an independent one with its own system. Comparing the results of studying a number of texts (for example, the language in a number of settlements or the language of different monuments) makes it possible either to identify them (find one system in them) or to establish a number of variants of the system (otherwise, a number of microsystems) included in one more general system (a macrosystem) or, finally, to recognise the presence of a number of systems (i.e., languages), otherwise to qualify the presence of one language or one language in several variants, or, finally, to establish the presence of two languages [5].

In the 10th and 11th centuries, the following types of language existed in ancient Russia:

1. The Church Slavonic language, which had a South Slavic basis and served the spheres of worship, church, philosophy, science, and high religious poetry.

2. Business language, in particular legal language, is used in domestic and foreign diplomacy and legal and economic relations [8].

3. The folklore language that served folk poetry and folk verbal artistic creativity.

These "languages" served the same society but were functionally differentiated. One of them served the spheres of worship, church, philosophy, science, and high religious poetry; the other was internal and external diplomacy; legal and economic relations; and the third was folk poetry and folk verbal artistic creativity in general. These "languages" were not completely differentiated from each other but interacted, sometimes very intensively and differently in different periods. For example, church-book elements penetrated into the language of business and legal monuments and even into the language of folklore [7].

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